

various aldehydes. The data regarding the m.p. and yield of these compounds are tabulated in Table I.

TABLE I—5-Oxo-2,6-disubstituted-2,3-dihydro-5H-[1,3,4]thiadiazolo[2,3-c][1,2,4]triazines

Sl. No.	R	R'	m.p. °C	yield %
a	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	203	40
b	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (3')	238	47
c	CH ₃	CH ₃ O, C ₆ H ₄ (3',4')	233	45
d	CH ₃	CH ₃ O, C ₆ H ₃ NO ₂ (3',4',6')	228	50
e	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	232	55
f	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (3')	228	59
g	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃ O, C ₆ H ₄ (3',4')	225	58
h	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃ O, C ₆ H ₃ NO ₂ (3',4',6')	250	51
i	C ₆ H ₅	HO, C ₆ H ₄ OOH ₂ (5',3')	236	52

All these compounds were crystallised from ethanol and gave satisfactory analysis for C, H and N.

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Reaction of Homophthalic Acid with *m*-Hydroxybenzoic Acid

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In general, 3-phenylisocoumarins¹⁻⁴ have been synthesised by direct condensation of homophthalic anhydride with aromatic hydrocarbon, phenols, phenolic ether, etc. using anhyd. AlCl₃ or stannous chloride as a condensing agent. It was later found that polyphosphoric acid was a good cyclodehydrating agent⁴ for the synthesis of 3-phenyl isocoumarins.

In continuation of our previous work⁵⁻⁸, we report here the condensation of homophthalic acid (I) with 3-hydroxybenzoic acid (IIb) in presence of polyphosphoric acid to furnish 3-(2'-carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenyl)-isocoumarin (III) followed by a neutral compound and 6'-hydroxy-1'-oxo-1H-indeno

(2',3' : 3,4)-isocoumarin (IV). III on either refluxing with phosphorus oxychloride in dry benzene or heating with polyphosphoric acid yielded IV. Solution of IV in acetone on methylation with methyl iodide in presence of potassium carbonate gave 6'-methoxy-1'-oxo-1H-indeno-(2',3' : 3,4)-isocoumarin.

Experimental

6'-Hydroxy-1'-oxo-1H-indeno (2',3' : 3,4) isocoumarin: A mixture of homophthalic acid (3.6 g), *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid (3.0 g) and commercial polyphosphoric acid (15 g) was taken in a hard glass test tube, fitted with anhydrous calcium chloride tube and heated at 140-45° for 1.5 h in a glycerol bath. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into crushed ice and left for a few h. The precipitate that separated was filtered and washed well with water. The crude product was triturated with aqueous sodium carbonate and allowed to stand for a few h. The solid product was filtered, washed well with water and crystallised from ethyl acetate as colourless crystals, m.p. 249-50°, (0.8 g) (Found : C, 72.73; H, 2.98. Calcd. for C₁₆H₈O₅; C, 72.71; H, 3.07%). IR : 2850, 1715, 1702, 1610 cm⁻¹. NMR (CDCl₃) : 7.2-7.8 (m, 6H, aromatic); 8.3 (m, 1H, C-8, peri-aromatic proton) and 10.0 (s, 1H, -OH).

3-(2'-Carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenyl)isocoumarin (III): The aqueous sodium carbonate filtrate obtained during the preparation of IV on acidification yielded a mixture of 3-(2'-carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenyl) isocoumarin, unreacted homophthalic acid and *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid. The mixture obtained was treated with hot water when homophthalic acid and *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid dissolved, whereas 3-(2'-carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenyl) isocoumarin remained undissolved. It was filtered hot and crystallised as colourless crystals, m.p. 182-88° (1.2 g) (Found : C, 68.01; H, 3.49. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₀O₅; C, 68.08; H, 3.54%). IR : 2680, 1720, 1695, 1650 cm⁻¹.

Cyclodehydration of III to 6'-hydroxy-1'-oxo-1H-indeno (2',3' : 3,4) isocoumarin (IV):

Method I: III (0.5 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) was refluxed with phosphorous oxychloride (3.5 ml) on a water bath for 4.5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the benzene layer was washed

successively with water, aqueous sodium carbonate (10%), water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and filtered. It was then concentrated when light yellow crystals separated, m.p. 247-49° (0.15 g).

Method II: III (0.2 g) was taken in a hard glass test tube and heated with polyphosphoric acid (4 g) on a glycerol bath at 140° for 1 h. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice and the solid separated was filtered and washed. The crude product was suspended in aqueous sodium carbonate and allowed to stand for 0.5 h. It was filtered, washed and crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 248-49° (0.075 g).

6'-Methoxy-1'-oxo-1H-indeno-(2',3':3,4)-isocoumarin: A solution of IV (0.2 g) in acetone (15 ml) was mixed with dry methyl iodide (5 ml) and anhyd. pot. carbonate (0.15 g). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h and filtered hot. The solvent was evaporated and the product crystallised in ethyl acetate as colourless needles, m.p. 225-27°. IR: 2970, 1710, 1605, 1510 cm^{-1} .

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Synthesis of 1-Arylpiperazine Mannich Bases and Amides of Ethyl 7-Hydroxycoumarin-4-acetate as Possible Antiinflammatory Agents

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COUMARIN ring has an easy accessibility in the biological systems as compared to the isomeric-isosteric chromone nucleus¹. Mannich bases of 7-hydroxycoumarins (umbelliferone derivatives) possess profound CNS stimulant activity²⁻¹⁰. In this case, the nature of the amine used as well as that of the substituents on the coumarin moiety have marked effect on the activity. Encouraging results obtained by us in the case of Mannich bases of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin with 1-arylpiperazine¹⁰ prompted us to undertake a parallel study

on the analogous Mannich bases of ethyl 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetate (I). Using 1-arylpiperazines (II), Mannich bases (III) of I were prepared. As a further modification, 1-arylpiperazine amides of 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid were also prepared by condensing I with II. These amides (IV) were expected to possess antiinflammatory activity in addition to the CNS activity.

I reacted with II in presence of paraformaldehyde and catalytic amount of KOH in refluxing EtOH to give III. III were characterised as ethyl-8-(4-aryl-1-piperazinylmethyl)-7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetates, based on the previous reports and the spectral data. To locate the position of the piperazinylmethyl residue on the coumarin nucleus, morpholine analogue (V) of III was prepared by a similar method. PMR spectrum (CDCl_3) of V showed two doublets at 6.63 ($J=9\text{Hz}$) and 7.43 ($J=9\text{Hz}$), each integrating for one proton, due to H_5 and H_6 , respectively. Thus, the position of the piperazinylmethyl residue at the 8-position in III was confirmed. To obtain further proof, IIIa was hydrolysed carefully and the resulting carboxylic acid (VI) was decarboxylated to obtain 8-(4-phenyl-1-piperazinylmethyl)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (VII); spectral data for which was consonant with the structure. VII could also be obtained by the reaction of 1-phenylpiperazine with 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, obtained by the condensation of resorcinol with ethyl acetoacetate, in the presence of paraformaldehyde in absolute alcohol. II on heating with excess I gave 7-hydroxy-4-[2-(4-aryl-1-piperazinyl)-2-oxoethyl]coumarins (IV).